

Minutes of the 58th Experimenters' Meeting The Cosener's House, Abingdon, 8th February 2017

(This document was finalised on 19th June 2017)

Present:

(DAH)	Dr David Hooper ^{2,3}	Secretary
(DK)	Dr Dirk Klugmann ³	
(GAP)	Dr Graham Parton ^{1,3}	
(GM)	Dr Graeme Marlton ⁵	
(GV)	Prof Geraint Vaughan ⁴	Chair
(HMAR)	Dr Hugo Ricketts ⁴	
(JR)	Dr Jolyon Reburn ³	

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Other abbreviations used in this document:

BLWP	Boundary-Layer Wind-Profiler
DOI	digital object identifier
EUCOS	EUMETNET Composite Observing System
ISP	Internet Service Provider
LD	Les Dean (NERC MSTRF site technician)
MST(R)(F)	Mesosphere-Stratosphere-Troposphere (Radar) (Facility)
NAWDEX	North Atlantic Waveguide and Downstream Impact Experiment
NERC	Natural Environment Research Council
STFC	Science and Technology Facilities Council
UPS	Uninterruptable Power Supply
UTC	Universal Time
v3/v4	MST Radar processing version number 3/4

1. Minutes of the previous meeting

The minutes of the 57th meeting were accepted without correction.

2. Matters arising

ACTION ITEM 47.2.1 DAH to modify the MST radar signal processing software, as soon as possible, to allow it to make use of updated Python programming libraries.

ONGOING

ACTION ITEM 47.2.2 DAH to ensure, as soon as possible, that MST radar data products generated by the latest version of the signal processing software are available for the entire observation archive.

ONGOING

ACTION ITEM 51.6.1 DAH to determine an improved method of applying the horizontal wind θ_s compensation factor so that its contribution to random errors is minimised.

COMPLETED

ACTION ITEM 57.1.1 DAH and CJW [Chris Walden] to put together a work plan to ensure that a new MST radar signal processing scheme is ready by the time of the next (58th) Experimenters' meeting.

ONGOING

DAH reported that he had made progress on the four action items above and that he would report on these in section 4g. Action 51.6.1 can be considered to be completed.

ACTION ITEM 51.4.1 DAH to increase the storage capacity of the Frongoch data logger so that communications failures do not lead to data loss.

ONGOING

No effort has been devoted to the item above.

ACTION ITEM 47.3.2 DAH to recreate cloud base altitude files, starting from 2nd November 2010, with the time stamps corrected.

ONGOING

DAH reported that he had made some progress on this, which he will report in section 4d.

ACTION ITEM 51.4.2 DAH to make the Met Office's model-comparison statistics for the MST radar permanently available to users if the Met Office will allow this.

ONGOING

No progress has been made on this.

ACTION ITEM 53.4.2 GAP and DAH to determine a way of providing retrospectively-determined data reliability details in a machine-readable format.

ONGOING

There was a general discussion on this item. Where data are known to be incorrect, it is clear that the files need to be removed from public view and then replaced. However, in the case of the MST Radar, there are times when one or more transmitters is down. Although the wind data do not appear to be affected, which is what most people will care above, parameters such as spectral width could be. Consequently it is necessary to find out what would be useful for potential users.

ACTION ITEM 58.1.1 DAH to consult with members of the data user community in order to establish the sort of instrument performance details that would be useful.

NEW

GAP thought that any files arising from this action would belong in the main data area of the archive, as opposed to being added as metadata.

It was agreed that a digital object identifier (DOI) should be assigned to the new version 4 MST Radar dataset (see section 4g). A DOI can already be assigned to the Vaisala WXT510 dataset, since the instrument has ceased operations and the dataset will not continue to grow.

ACTION ITEM 58.1.2 GAP to assign a digital object identifier (DOI) to the NERC MSTRF's Vaisala WXT510 dataset.

NEW

3. Facility Report - DAH

Full details of facility and instrument performance issues can be found at http://mst.nerc.ac.uk/cgi-bin/mstlog_public/mst_event_search.py.

3a) Data Management

GAP gave a report on the how the MSTRF's data have been accessed through the Centre for Environmental Data Analysis (CEDA). These statistics are publicly visible through http://public-stats.ceda.ac.uk/cgi-bin/stats/download_stats_public.py?selpath=%2Fbadc%2Fmst%2F. There were 31 users during the past 12 months. These were predominantly from the atmospheric science and engineering communities. Just under half of them were from the UK. A variety of other countries were represented, including India and China. Surface met and wind data accounted for 40% of downloads. GAP noted that some users were accessing MST radar data products that are not derived from the latest (version 3) processing scheme. He pointed out that these statistics do not cover data access through the jasmin system or quick-look data plots. GV commented that these statistics were proving very useful in the context of reporting to NERC. It is important to be able to demonstrate that there is a large amount of use of long term datasets.

3b) Electricity - DAH

As usual, the Uninterruptable Power Supply (UPS) units experienced several instances of electricity supply problems. In most cases, the problem lasted for approximately 1 s. In one case, on 20th July 2016, it lasted for 5 s. The unit TX5 continues to send out frequent "system warmstart" messages, which appear to relate to (computer) network problems.

3c) Telecommunications

There was a loss of internet connection to the site between approximately 06:40 and 08:15 UTC on 21st July 2016. The Internet Service Provider's (ISP's) website described the cause as "*a major non-geographic network outage affecting all connections*". A second outage began at approximately 10:30 UTC on 17th October 2016. DAH was expecting to have to wait at least one or two days for the problem to be sorted. However, the connection was reestablished by 12:45 UTC the same day without an Openreach engineer having visited the site. A third outage, which began at approximately 10:30 UTC on 17th November 2016, and which affected both the telephone and internet connections, was caused by an extreme wind event - see below. The connections were not restored until 3 days later. It is thought that this event was also responsible for a problem with the alarm phone line, which was not repaired until mid January 2017.

DAH passed on details of the 17th November event to all of the scientists who he thought might be interested in extreme wind events. David Wareing, who lives in Aberystwyth, reported that numerous trees had been brought down in the surrounding area and that his greenhouse had been badly damaged. However, Les Dean (LD), who lives a few miles to the south of Aberystwyth had noticed nothing out of the ordinary. Other reports suggest that the destruction caused by the event had been confined to a rela-

tively narrow path. Caroline Bulpett, from the Met Office, also showed an interest in this event beyond the operational reasons for which DAH had contacted her. She shared images from the Met Office's weather radars for the regions through which the wind event had passed. Although the word "tornado" had been used in media reports - e.g. <http://www.bbc.co.uk/news/uk-wales-38014691> - both Caroline and GV thought that a microburst was responsible. The MST Radar observations show an increase in wind speeds at the lowest observable range gates during the period of interest. Owing to the loss of phone and internet connections, the Frongoch surface wind data for this period were overwritten before they could be downloaded. However, DAH examined the wind data from the WXT520 sonic anemometer. These showed wind speeds of $< 5 \text{ m s}^{-1}$ prior to 10:30 UTC, 13.9 m s^{-1} at 10:32, 15.8 m s^{-1} at 10:41, and back to $< 5 \text{ m s}^{-1}$ from 10:49 UTC. GV commented that it might have been possible to base a science study on this event if the Frongoch surface wind data had been available.

3d) Miscellaneous

GV gave an update on NERC's National Capability evaluation exercise. The purpose of the review that was carried out in early 2016 was simply to establish whether Facilities had been achieving their stated aims. NERC must now decide, based on the results, which Facilities will be invited to apply for funding renewal. It is anticipated that there will be a first round of renewals in late 2017/early 2018 and a second round a year later. NERC Centres, such as the National Centre for Atmospheric Science (NCAS), can now fund long term observation programmes through their science plans. This would reduce the amount of funding required directly from NERC. If both the MSTRF and the Chilbolton Facility for Atmospheric and Radio Research (CFARR) are invited to apply for funding renewal, it is likely that they will do so as a single, combined facility.

DAH reported that NERC had carried out a "conditions survey" for each of its Facilities during the latter part of 2016. The aim was to identify the likely requirements for infrastructure maintenance and replacement over the next 5 - 10 years. The survey for the MSTRF identified the electrical distribution system and emptying/replacing the septic tank as high priority issues. NERC have allocated money to the MSTRF to cover all of the requirements highlighted in the report. The electrical work is due to be completed before the end of March 2017. However, it has taken DAH over a year to set the contract owing to the government's "Facilities Management" rules, which came into effect in 2016. These are designed to channel all estates work through large, central suppliers. LD has drawn DAH's attention to the fact that willow saplings are once again taking over parts of the antenna array. Consequently this is another estates issue that requires urgent attention.

During the latter part of 2016, DAH helped visual artist Mat Chivers to make use of cloud data from the MSTRF's laser ceilometer for a work entitled "(Its Not) Black and White (Aberystwyth)". This was displayed at the "Harmonic Distortion" exhibition, which was held at the PM/AM gallery in London between November 2016 and February 2017 -

<http://www.pmam.org/exhibitions/mat-chivers-harmonic-distortion/>.

The exhibition featured artworks based on other atmospheric and oceanic datasets.

On 5th July 2016, DAH received an anonymous phone call threatening to petrol bomb him and/or the MST radar. The caller began by saying that he wanted to talk about "solar radiation management" and so is clearly a follower of the chemtrail conspiracy theory. Another member of RAL staff received a similar phone call, apparently because he had inherited a phone number that was still shown on the MSTRF's website as a contact one. The matter was reported to the police.

DAH reminded attendees of the forthcoming 15th International Workshop on Technical and Scientific Aspects of MST Radar (MST15) - <http://www2.rish.kyoto-u.ac.jp/mst15/index.html> - which is due to be held in Japan in late May 2017. Both DAH and GM were hoping to attend. DAH also reported that he had been invited to visit the Leibniz Institute for Atmospheric Physics in Kühlungsborn, Germany in mid March 2017. He will give a presentation on his mesospheric research

and discuss the potential for collaborative work.

4. NERC Instrument Report - DAH

In the cases of the Campbell Scientific surface met sensors, the Vaisala WXT520 surface met and wind sensors, and the Vaisala LD40 laser ceilometer, data since August 2015 are not currently available through CEDA in standard-format files. In each case, the updated file creation software is almost ready for use. However, since DAH has had to prioritise the creation of the version 4 MST Radar data processing scheme - see section 4g - he has not had time to complete these other tasks.

4a) Campbell Scientific surface met sensors

Refer to main comment for section 4.

4b) Campbell Scientific surface wind sensors

The only problem to have affected these sensors was caused by the loss of the telephone and internet connection to the site between 17th and 20th November 2016 - see section 3c. This resulted in the loss of data for the period 02:15 - 22:38 UTC on 17th November.

4c) Vaisala WXT520 surface met and wind sensors

Refer to main comment for section 4.

GV noted the high level of demand for surface met data, as reported by GAP in section 3a. He suggested that DAH should prioritise the release of either the Campbell Scientific surface met data or the WXT520 data over other tasks.

ACTION ITEM 58.4.1 DAH to prioritise the release of the latest surface met data to CEDA.

NEW

4d) Vaisala LD40 laser ceilometer

DAH has created a solution for the timing problem that affects this instrument. The date-time stamps of observations are generated by the instrument's internal, free-running clock. Not only can this drift by the order of a minute in a month, but it resets every time that power to the instrument is interrupted. DAH's solution can automatically estimate the observation time (typically accurate to within one minute) as long as a gap in data acquisition does not wrap around midnight.

4e) Sky Cameras

DAH reported that he had publicly released the first time-lapse video based on images taken by the original sky camera - <http://cedadocs.ceda.ac.uk/1271>. The video shows a rapidly-growing cumulus cloud, which becomes a cumulonimbus with a clear anvil. This and subsequent videos are being published under a Creative Commons Attribution license, which means that anyone may download and distribute copies. DAH had deposited two more videos with the CEDA document repository, but GAP had recommend that he wait to release them until a new version of the repository goes live. The domain name will change from cedadocs.badc.rl.ac.uk to cedadocs.ceda.ac.uk (note that the link above uses the new address).

Refer to next section for details relating to Sky-Camera-2.

4f) Noctilucent Cloud (NLC) Camera

DAH has used the known position of stars that pass through the NLC camera's field of view in order to determine its pointing direction. This is important for being able to determine the geographical location of NLCs. An unexpected conclusion from this analysis is that "perspective distortion" must be

taken into account. This is the familiar effect of vertical lines converging to a point above the middle of the image when a camera is tilted upwards from the horizontal. This causes the relationship between image x and y coordinates and the azimuth and elevation angles to be non-linear. The stellar method grew out of an exercise that DAH originally undertook with a Work Experience student. The aim had been to identify a star (Arcturus) that was visible as it passed through the Sky Camera's field of view. He adapted the method with a subsequent Work Experience student in order to determine the pointing direction for Sky-Camera-2. However, he quickly switched his attention to the NLC Camera, which offered multiple stars to work with.

4g) MST Radar

DAH began by presenting model-comparison statistics, which had been prepared by Caroline Bulpett of the Met Office. The number of observations received daily by the EUMETNET Composite Observing System (EUCOS) has remained fairly constant over the period. There were only a few days when this dropped significantly and these were associated with known internet problems. The EUCOS root mean square (RMS) wind mean vector difference values were only rarely above the 5.0 m s^{-1} target maximum. The Met Office's UKV model-comparison statistics also show good data quality over the period.

DAH then gave a general instrument performance report. MST Radar Cartesian data for the period 18th - 20th November 2016 are not currently available through CEDA owing to erroneously-restricted time-altitude coverage. There is a known bug in the signal processing software that prevents older observations from being removed from the work flow when the external internet connection is lost (see section 3c for details of this incident). This leads to the time-continuity quality control algorithm being applied over more than the standard one hour. The data gaps can be filled by reprocessing the radial data.

A new type of interference was first seen on 4th May 2016, i.e. shortly before the previous Experimenters' meeting. Its primary characteristic is clearly-erroneous near-zero horizontal wind speeds at altitudes of around 10 km, plus/minus a few km. It was seen again on 2nd - 5th July 2016, inclusive, on 11th July, on 7th - 9th August, inclusive, and on 15th and 16th August. The Cartesian files for these days are not currently available through CEDA. LD had suggested that the source of the interference could be sporadic E echoes that have been range-aliased from ionospheric altitudes. DAH had attempted to manually block the Met Office's data feed whenever he noticed the problem. However, this still resulted in some affected data being released and in unaffected data being blocked. There was one case of old-school interference between 18th and 19th December 2016.

There have been many instances when the output power of one of the transmitters has been reported as being below expected for the duration of a single dwell. However, there has been only one case each when transmitters TXB, TXC, TXD, and TXE have been out of action for longer periods. A blown fuse was the cause in three cases. In the case of TXE, an "analogue error" was caused by the heater final voltage drifting out of the permitted range. LD subsequently replaced the voltage reference circuit.

The beam steering unit has been sending frequent but sporadic "[CRITICAL] System Error detected" messages over the past year. These appear to relate to problems with the database software rather than with the radar hardware. DAH and LD carried out a reboot of Tiberius, the beam steering computer, on 1st July 2016 in an attempt to clear any problems. However, this did not appear to reduce the frequency of the messages.

LD replaced beam steering unit 3 on 30th June 2016 after it had reported a low supply voltage. Beam steering units 81, 82, 91, and 92, which are fed from the same power divider, began to be sporadically unresponsive on 5th November 2016. The radar was stopped on both the 3rd and 17th January 2017 so that LD could investigate further. He found the dc voltages were getting through and so suspects that the problem is for the radio frequency.

DAH concluded with a report on the new version 4 (v4) data processing scheme that he has been developing. This currently uses version 3 (v3) Cartesian data files as input. The main difference is that the v4 horizontal wind data represent averages over a nominal period of 33 minutes (6 cycles) whereas the v3 winds are single cycle estimates (v3). This significantly reduces the random measurement error and slightly improves the time-altitude coverage. A secondary difference lies in the way that the v4 scheme calculates the aspect sensitivity compensation factor for the horizontal wind speeds. This corrects for the fact that an off-vertical beam's effective zenith angle tends to be slightly smaller than the nominal angle as a result of aspect sensitivity. The v3 scheme uses the ratio of signal powers observed at zenith angles of 4.2° and 6.0°. Only a single beam pointing direction is used for observations made at 4.2° off-vertical, whereas four (with azimuths separated by 90°) are used at 6.0°. DAH has previously shown that the signal power tends to vary as a function of azimuth. Consequently the v3 compensation factor is sub-optimal in its representative. The v4 scheme instead uses the ratio of signal powers observed at zenith angles of 0.0° and 6.0°, which is more robust. The new software is nearly ready for use.

DAH asked for suggestions of periods that users would like to see processed using the new scheme. He would like some feedback on the new files, particularly before bulk processing the entire archive. He noted that the version 4.0 files are not yet compliant with the new NCAS data standards. GV requested that DAH create version 4 files for the NAWDEX campaign period.

5. Guest Instrument Report

HMAR reported that the performance of the Elight lidar has improved following a 2 year period when it was not working well. It has not yet been upgraded for water vapour sensing capability. The Leosphere lidar is working again, but has not been aligned. The Raman lidar is working well and was in operation during the NAWDEX campaign - see section 6a. The boundary-layer wind-profiler (BLWP) has been back at Capel Dewi since September 2016, but has suffered from a variety of problems. The mobile laboratory (which is basically a caravan) proved to be a very useful work space during the NAWDEX campaign. The SAOZ ozone-measuring instrument is currently working well.

If the BLWP can be brought back into working order before the end of March, there are plans to run a short campaign of radiosonde launches from the radar site. This is to follow up on Chris Lee's discovery that there is a systematic difference between the wind speeds measured by the MST Radar and by the BLWP. Chris had previously looked for a radio physics explanation. However, it's possible that it could have been the result of a slight (i.e. 1°) misalignment of the BLWP's vertical beam. It should be possible to achieve an accuracy of approximately 0.25° using the BLWP's spirit levels.

6. Science and technical presentations

6a) North Atlantic Waveguide and Downstream Impact Experiment (NAWDEX) - HMAR

This international campaign was conducted between 19th September and 16th October 2016. It was motivated by the fact that one of the limitations for longer-term forecast accuracy is the inability of models to represent sufficiently-large horizontal gradients of potential vorticity across the jet stream.

Four research aircraft took part in the campaign: the German High Altitude and Long Range Research Aircraft (HALO) and Falcon, the French Service of Instrumented Aircraft for Environmental Research (SAFIRE) Falcon, and the UK's Facility for Airborne Atmospheric Measurements (FAAM) BAe-146. The MSTRF supported the campaign both through radar observations and through hosting equipment - mainly the lidars.

The MST Radar site turned out to be well placed, since it was sometimes in an upstream location and sometimes in a downstream one. The water vapour, Raman, and ozone/aerosol lidars were all in operation (GV added that he is learning how to access data from the Met Office's lidar network). The second

week of the campaign was particularly good for lidar observations since the skies were predominantly clear.

Thirty one radiosondes were launched from the site during the course of the campaign. Six were launched on 11th October - the most in a single day. The team also experimented with "windsonds" - <http://windsond.com/> - a cheaper alternative to radiosondes. The sensor package is much smaller and lighter than a radiosonde and so it can be launched with a much-lower-volume balloon. It is designed to detach from the balloon at an altitude of up to 5 km and to be recovered and reused. It doesn't require a full ground station, but uses a small antenna that can connect to a laptop through a dongle. HMAR found that its software was much easier to use than the equivalent software for radiosondes. He is aiming to make further use of the windsonds.

Not much analysis has yet taken place of the campaign data. However, GV is hoping to find a student to take this on.

6b) Transport of Canadian forest fire smoke to the UK - GV

This presentation was based on work carried out by a summer student. The Raman lidar observations during the night of 23/24 May 2016 showed a number of tropospheric layers with enhanced lidar ratios. These were too optically thin to be interpreted as clouds. Back trajectory data from NOAA's HYSPLIT model indicate that the air had been transported from western Canada, where forest fires had been burning. These particular fires were related to an El Niño event, which gave rise to temperatures of 32°C, but relative humidities of only 17%. Forward trajectories starting one week earlier in north-western Alberta mostly ended up over the British Isles. The student The smoke could be seen moving eastward in observations made by 3 satellites: NASA's CALIPSO, the Ozone Mapping Profiler Suite (OMPS), and EUMETSAT. The Met Office's Jenoptik lidars proved to be very useful since there is a dense network of them across the British Isles. GV commented that the student had achieved a lot in 10 weeks of work. He had been particularly good at making scientific contacts through social media, which had led to him including satellite data in the study. His work built on that of a succession of vacation students over recent years.

6c) A method for assessing radar profiler performance - DK

DK presented a statistical method for evaluating radar profiler performance. A similar approach has previously been used by Meteo France for evaluating lidar/ceilometer performance. The method is based on creating a two dimensional histogram based on typically 24 hours' worth of data. Data are binned according to their altitude and according to the profiler parameter of interest, e.g. signal power, signal to noise ratio, or reflectivity. These can then be used to compare the performance of different radars, e.g. to determine their sensitivities. DK presented some sample data taken from the NCAS mobile Ka-band radar (known as Kepler). The technique could be adapted for (amongst other things) different types of radars, including wind-profiling ones, for nowcasting and weather forecasting, and for climate monitoring.

6d) A comparison of rainfall measurement and detection techniques at the NERC MST Radar site - DAH

This work was carried out by Oliver King through the RAL Vacation Student scheme during the summer of 2016. The primary aim of the project was to compare measurements made by the (Campbell Scientific) tipping bucket rain gauge and the (Vaisala WXT510 and WXT520) piezoelectric precipitation sensor. The tipping bucket is known to be prone to blockages and mechanical problems, which can prevent it from making measurements. Although the piezoelectric sensor does not suffer from these problems, it is known to have difficulties detecting very light rain. A secondary aim of the project was to evaluate the usefulness of precipitation detection/avoidance flags provided by the Vaisala LD40 laser ceilometer and the MST radar signal processing. The laser ceilometer files provide a precipitation index, which indicates (0) no precipitation, (1) light, (2) moderate, and (3) heavy precipitation. It is known that

the precipitation detection algorithm can confuse a very low cloud base for precipitation. The MST radar spectral processing has an algorithm designed to avoid hydrometeor scatter signals. This is to ensure that only clear air scatter signals contribute to the wind profile estimates.

The tipping bucket rain gauge and piezoelectric sensor typically showed precipitation at the same times. There was mostly a good qualitative match during rainfall events, although there could sometimes be large differences, which are hard to explain. The differences between the daily integrated totals for the two instruments show a large degree of variability. The LD40's precipitation index was found to be broadly correlated with the rain rates from the previous two instruments. However, a running mean value was found to be more reliable than a single observation value. The MST radar's precipitation avoidance flag was shown to be a poor indicator of actual precipitation. However, it was designed to avoid any possible contamination of the clear air signals rather than to identify hydrometeor scatter. Moreover, since the lowest range gate is 1600 m above the radar, any hydrometeors that are seen will have travelled a significant horizontal distance by the time they reach the ground, if they do not evaporate beforehand.

DAH reported that he had been very pleased with his Vacation Student and that he was trying to get another one for the summer of 2017. This year's project will be to examine the signature of clouds seen by the MST Radar. This will rely on backscatter data from the laser ceilometer.

7. Any Other Business

GV summarised that DAH should prioritise his work as follows:

- a) make the the v4 MST Radar data processing software operational
- b) make the latest Campbell Scientific surface met data available
- c) make a start on the estates work

The date of the next meeting was provisionally set for the first week of July 2017.